

A Comparative Study of Arts and Engineering Students on Mental Health

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Abstract: Mental health of the learner is very important for efficient learning and proper development of personality. The main objective of the present study was to assess the levels of mental health and gender differences of Arts and Engineering students of colleges of Vijayapur, Karnataka. Mental Health Inventory was administered on students with Socio-demographic sheet. 't' test was carried for statistical analysis and interpretation. The results clearly revealed that Engineering students are found to have higher mental health than Arts students. Significant gender differences in mental health are also noted in the present investigation.

Keywords: Mental health, personality, self-growth, adjustment, behavior, social environment, psychosomatic problems, happiness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The mental health is an individual's capacity to form harmonious adjustments to one's social and physical environments. Menninger (1945) defined mental health as the adjustment of human beings to the world and to each other with a maximum of effectiveness and happiness. It is an ability to maintain an even temper, an alert intelligence, socially considerate behavior and a happy disposition. Mental health can be described as absence of symptoms of maladjustment, be they mild or severe. The person who is mentally healthy person is free from all types of maladjustment (Klein, 1956). Jahoda (1958) has said that aspects of attitudes toward self, growth and development, self-actualization, integration of personality and mastery of the environment must be considered in judging whether a person is mentally healthy or not.

Mental health of the learner is very important for efficient learning and proper development of personality. A child is born in a home where he remains in the constant company of his mother in the formative years of his infancy. Traditionally, it is said the mother is equal to hundred teachers. The impressions and experiences which a child has in these formative years leave permanent and indelible. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Mental health is a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully and is able to make a contribution to his or her own community.

From this, one can conclude that mental health has two important aspects. It is both individual and social. The individual aspect connotes that the individual is internally adjusted. He is self-confident, adequate and free from internal conflicts and tensions or inconsistencies. He is skillful enough to be able to adapt to new situations. But he achieves this internal adjustment in a social setup. Society has certain value systems, customs and traditions by which it governs itself and promotes the general welfare of its members. It is within this social framework that the internal adjustment has to be built up. Only then, the individual becomes a person who is acceptable as a member of the society.

Mental health can and should be a live experience for student. The teacher's part is greater in mental health education than in physical health education because some of the mental health problems are caused by school situations and others are aggravated by school conditions. They can help to establish a therapeutic environment for children who have problems of living. There are many who fail to realize the best of their potential, who find it impossible to be happy and who suffer from minor mental and psychosomatic disturbances.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Satdev Verma and Pushkrit Gupta (2011) studied the role of emotional intelligence in relation to mental health and adjustment of secondary school students. The result of research revealed that correlation between emotional intelligence and mental health is significant and another correlation between emotional intelligence and adjustment also proved significant. The t-ratio regarding emotional intelligence between male and female is significant but after considering adjustment the result came to just opposite ie, negative.

Chandra Shekhar et al. (2012) conducted a research on Self-concept and mental health of school dents under the impact of television viewing, results showed that there was a no significant difference in television viewing between the Govt. and Private school students as far as their self concept was concerned where as a significant difference was found in their mental health. Tejpreet Kang, Asha Chawla (2009) studied the mental health: A study of rural adolescents. The sample consisted of rural adolescent boys and girls. The tools used were socio economic status scale. Mental health check list. Major findings of the study were: A non-significant gender difference across mental health status but a significant difference in somatic health status of adolescent boys and 59 girls Boys were found to be having better somatic health status as compared to girls.

Ketan Dholakiya and Ashwin Jansari (2005) made a study of mental health of de students residing in affected & non-affected earth quake area and gender The sample comprised of 120 students of Kutch district of Gujarat state. Tools were used Kumar's mental health check list. The major findings of the study revealed that the students residing in earth quake area had more frustration. Boys showed more uneasiness and sleeplessness compared to girls. But girls showed more nervousness than boys.

3. METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

- To investigate whether Arts and Engineering undergraduate students differ significantly in mental health.
- To examine gender differences in Mental health of the students studying in Arts and Engineering students.

Hypotheses:

- Arts and Engineering undergraduate students differ significantly in their mental health.
- Male and female undergraduate students differ significantly from each other in their mental health.

Variables:

- Independent variable: Arts and Engineering stream of education
- Dependent variable: Mental health

Sample:

In order to examine the above-mentioned hypotheses, a total sample of 120 graduate students from Arts (60) and Engineering (60) faculty were selected from Government First Grade college, Vijayapur and SIET, Vijayapur. The sample from each faculty consists of 30 male and 30 female undergraduate students. The age range of sample is 18 to 22. Purposive sampling method was adopted to select the student sample.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The students included were of the age group of 18 to 22.
2. Undergraduate students were included from only arts and engineering faculty.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. The students below the age group of 18 and above the age group of 22 were not included as the sample for study.
2. Other faculty apart from arts and engineering were not included.

Measures Used:**Mental Health Inventory (Dr. Jagadish and Dr. Srivatsava):**

This inventory is developed by Jagadish and Srivastava (1988) which is consisting of 56 items distributed along 6 dimensions of mental health, they are positive self evaluation, perception of reality, integration of personality, autonomy, group oriented attitudes, environmental mastery. There are 24 positive and 32 negative items and the scoring is of Likert type. The inventory has four response categories namely always, often, rarely and never. A score of 4,3,2 and 1 is assigned to response category of positive statement and for negative item the scoring is reversed. Thus, one is considered as well as total. The reliability of the inventory has been found to be 0.73 and the validity is quite satisfactory (0.54).

Statistical Techniques:

- Descriptive statistics (Mean and SD).
- 't' test was carried out to find out the significant difference between male and female undergraduate students.

4. RESULTS**Table no. 1: Means, SDs and t-values of mental health in two courses (N=120)**

Course		PSE	POR	IOP	AUT	GOA	EM	TMH
Engineering	Mean	30.65	27.35	39.4	25.9	31.9	31.15	186.7
	SD	3.29	3.28	3.15	3.89	4.13	3.86	21.6
Arts	Mean	28.45	24.21	34.72	22.18	27.84	26.81	164.21
	SD	3.09	3.16	4.31	3.39	4.85	3.57	22.37
't' values		3.77**	5.34**	6.79**	5.58**	4.93**	6.39**	5.60**

**Significant at 0.01 level

Table no. 2: Means, SDs and t-values of mental health in two categories of gender (N=120)

Gender		PSE	POR	IOP	AUT	GOA	EM	TMH
Male	Mean	31.25	30.39	38.19	28.71	32.54	31.59	192.67
	SD	3.51	3.5	4.14	3.74	4.48	3.21	22.58
Female	Mean	29.27	28.41	36.12	25.62	30.57	29.42	179.41
	SD	3.43	3.23	4.18	3.65	3.6	3.88	21.97
't' values		4.41**	4.55**	3.85**	6.47**	3.75**	4.72**	4.61**

**Significant at 0.01 level

5. DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the mean, SD and t-values of mental health of the students belonging to arts and engineering UG courses of education. It is observed that the Engineering course respondents have scored higher mean of 30.65 than Arts courses respondents 28.45 in the dimension of positive self- evaluation (PSE). The t-values on the mental health dimension positive self- evaluation (PSE) is significant at 3.77 which clearly shows that there are significant differences in the mental health of students belonging to different streams. Similarly, the same results are obtained in other dimensions of mental health, like, perception of reality (POR), integration of personality (IOP), autonomy (AUT), group oriented attitude (GOA), environmental mastery (EM) and total mental health (MH). The Engineering course students show the higher level of mental health. It is believed that they are more exposed to a variety of knowledge, various entrance tests for the entry of the courses, information, and exposure to health awareness, as a result of which the health practices, healthy attitudes and lifestyles are developed in a more desirable way.

On the similar way in the perception of reality (PR) dimension the mean score of Engineering students is higher 27.35 than Arts students 24.21. The higher mean score indicates that Engineering student's perception of reality is higher in comparison with Arts students. There is a significant difference (t-3.54 significant at 0.01 level) between Engineering and Arts students which clearly indicates that Engineering course knowledge increases the ability to perceive reality also increases.

In the dimension of integration of personality (IOP), Engineering students have scored a higher mean 39.40 compared to Arts course students 34.72 mean. Once again Engineering course education helps the students in integration of personality. The Engineering students develop personality integration because their course contents and approach develop healthy personality that equalizes the psychic forces of the person. The t-value of 6.79 is significant at 0.01 level which distinguishes significant differences between the two streams of education at UG courses.

In the dimension of autonomy (AUT) we can see the mean score of both Engineering and Arts course of education. The Engineering students mean is 25.9 and for Arts is 22.18. The Engineering student respondents are more autonomous than the Arts course students. The Engineering courses make them to become more autonomous by inculcating the essential skills in becoming self-reliant and self-confident. There is significant difference (t=5.58 significant at 0.05 level) between Engineering and Arts students. It can be noticed that in the dimension of group oriented attitude (GOA), the mean score of Engineering course students is 31.9 and Arts students is 27.84. The t-value 4.93 which is significant at 0.01 level. The Engineering students have more group oriented attitude and comparatively Arts students have less group oriented attitude.

The students of Engineering course have more group-oriented attitudes compare to Arts course students. The professional students are more goal oriented, set realistic goals, they work hard to fulfill those goals, since their course structure is practical oriented, they work in groups and teams. These make them to imbibe group-oriented attitudes. In the dimension of environmental mastery (EM), the mean score of Engineering students is 31.15 and Arts students are 26.81 and the t-value is 6.393 which is significant at 0.01 level. Thus, there is higher environmental mastery among Engineering students than the Arts students. There is a significant difference in the Engineering and Arts students' environmental mastery dimension of mental health. Similarly, the mean score of total mental health (TMH) of Engineering students is 186.67 and non-professional students are 164.21 and the t-value is 5.602 significant at 0.01 level. Thus the Engineering course is proved to be significant in producing significant differences in all mental health dimensions of the sample.

Table 2 shows the mean, SD's and t-values of mental health in male and female samples. It is noticed that the male students have a mean of 192.67 in the dimension of Total Mental Health and the females have a mean of 179.41 in this dimension, the t-value of 4.61 which is significant at 0.01 levels speaks that there are significant gender differences in mental health of this dimension. Therefore, males are found to have significantly higher mental health than the females. In a similar way in the dimensions of mental health POR, IOP, AUT, GOA and EM, there are significant gender differences in the mental health.

6. CONCLUSIONS

- There is significant difference in all the dimensions of mental health between Arts and Engineering Undergraduate (UG) students.
- The engineering UG students have higher mental health scores than Arts UG students.
- There are significant gender differences in all the areas of mental health.
- The males are found to have higher mental health scores than females.

Limitations:

1. The present study restricted only to Vijayapur city.
2. The samples are not classified as urban and rural students.
3. The intermediate, job oriented diploma (JODC) and other branch UG students are not taken as samples in this study.

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